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Title: Enrichment of rare earth elements as environmental tracers of contamination by acid mine drainage in salt marshes; a new perspective

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Corresponding Author: Mr JOAQUÍN DELGADO, Dr

Corresponding Author's Institution: UNIVERSIDAD DE HUELVA

First Author: JOAQUÍN DELGADO, Dr

Order of Authors: JOAQUÍN DELGADO, Dr; Rafael Pérez-López; Laura Galván ; José Miguel Nieto ; Tomasz Boski

Abstract: Rare earth elements (REE) were analyzed in surface sediments from the Guadiana Estuary (SW Iberian Pyrite Belt). NASC-normalized REE patterns show clearly convex curvatures in middle-REE (MREE) with respect to light- and heavy-REE, indicating acid-mixing processes between fluvial waters affected by acid mine drainage (AMD) and seawater. However, REE distributions in the mouth show slightly LREE-enriched and flat patterns, indicating saline-mixing processes typical of the coastal zone. NASC-normalized ratios (La/Gd and La/Yb) do not discriminate between both mixing processes in the estuary. Instead, a new parameter (EMREE) has been applied to measure the curvature in the MREE segment. The values of EMREE>0 are indicative of acid signatures and their spatial distribution reveal the existence of two decantation zones from flocculation processes related to drought periods and flood events. Studying REE fractionation through the EMREE may serve as a good proxy for AMD-pollution in estuarine environments comparing with the traditional methods.

Letter to the editor of Marine Pollution Bulletin.

31.01.2012

Dear Editor,

Herewith we submit a manuscript entitled: "Enrichment of rare earth elements as environmental tracers of contamination by acid mine drainage in salt marshes; a new perspective". The main aim of the paper is to utilize rare earth elements (REE) geochemistry as a tool to evaluate pollution by acid mine drainage (AMD) in current estuarine sediments. The goals of the study could be of interest to the Marine Pollution Bulletin readership for the following reasons:

1. **Environmental importance.** Sediment samples were collected from an estuary to show that, despite little evidence of anomalous metal concentrations, REE fractionation revealed impacts of AMD discharges. These results lead us to a reconsideration of the traditionally thought "unpolluted" environment when it was compared to nearby estuaries.
2. **Scientific merit.** In previous studies, we proposed a new metric (E_{MREE} parameter) for recognizing and quantifying the effects of acid mine drainage, based on the fractionation of MREE from both LREE and HREE, in the S. Domingos mine area. In the current study, we use this new methodology for the first time as a useful proxy for assessing the impact of these mining districts downstream, into estuarine systems probably affected by pollution produced in the inner zones of them fluvial basins (Guadiana estuary in the study case).
3. **Originality.** After this study, it seems to be that the traditional methods based on the shale-normalized (La/Gd) and (La/Yb) ratios in order to differentiate the acid- and salt-mixing processes are sometimes ambiguous and could conduct to erroneous interpretation in slightly contaminated estuaries. Instead, given the success of the novel E_{MREE} parameter, its extension to the scientific community is strongly recommended to study the water mixing processes in AMD-affected estuaries. Hence, we think that this article can be extensively quoted in other works.

None of the data, ideas and interpretations has previously been published. All co-authors have collaborated in the manuscript and agree to its submission to Marine Pollution Bulletin. We are looking forward to hearing from you and hope you will consider our manuscript for publication in your journal.

Yours sincerely,

Joaquín Delgado.

Title of the manuscript:

“Enrichment of rare earth elements as environmental tracers of contamination by acid mine drainage in salt marshes; a new perspective”

Order of Authors:

Joaquín Delgado ^{a,*}, Rafael Pérez-López ^{a,b}, Laura Galván ^c, José Miguel Nieto ^a, Tomasz Boski ^d

Institutional affiliations:

^a Department of Geology, University of Huelva, Campus ‘El Carmen’, 21071, Huelva, Spain

^b Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research, IDÆA - CSIC, Jordi Girona 18, 08034, Barcelona, Spain

^c Department of Geodynamics and Palaeontology, University of Huelva, Campus ‘El Carmen’, 21071, Huelva, Spain

^d Centre for Marine and Environmental Research, University of Algarve, 8005-139, Faro, Portugal

Corresponding author:

Joaquín Delgado, Department of Geology, University of Huelva.

Campus ‘El Carmen’, 21071, Huelva, Spain.

Tel.: +34-95-921-9826; fax: +34-95-921-9810, e-mail: joaquin.delgado@dgeo.uhu.es.

Dear Charles Sheppard Chief Editor of Marine Pollution Bulletin,

We really appreciate again the time that reviewers and editor have invested in improving our paper. We have corrected the mistypes and made all suggested changes on the revised manuscript following the reviewer suggestion (when applicable, see below).

Below we have included a detailed answer to all specific comments of the reviewers and our response to each one (in *red-bold type*).

Yours sincerely,
J. Delgado.-

Reviewers' comments:

The ms is very well organized, objectives of the work are clear and significant and the authors go to the point to present the results. Two things should be polished in the paper: i) description of figures, parameters and area of study are not always as explicit as should be. This makes difficult to follow the discussion and verified the accuracy of conclusions ii) In some parts of the discussion are given statements like "it is similar to" or "is moderately", supported by the data from Tables and Figures, but the values they use to provide the conclusions values are given in the text. Also, some of the conclusions should be better explained/reasoned.

SPECIFIC COMMENTS:

Page 2. ABSTRACT. Introduction, research highlights and conclusions are well organized, descriptive and very helpful to understand the manuscript. That's why I think the Abstract could be a bit better organized to be as clear as the rest of the paper.

The abstract has been improved.

Line 6. NASC acronym should be described in the abstract.

The description has been made.

Lines 4 and 10. The terms Guadiana Estuary and Mouth are used differently in the text. I assumed that the authors are referring to two different parts of Guadiana Estuary (the inland Estuary and part closer to the coast) but it's not clear and prevents the full comprehension of that part.

Clarification of significance has been included: mouth (closer to the coastal area).

Line 22 "in relation to" instead of "comparing with"

The change has been made.

Page 3.

Line 10. "the estuarine processes controlling the flux or fate". ¿Flux or fate?

The sentence has been corrected: "the estuarine processes controlling the flux and the behavior"...

Line 34. Reference after AMD.

References have been included.

Line 34. Rephrase as "In order to be better able to."

Done.

Page 4.

Line 59. "spread over more than A hundred"
The change has been made.

Page 5.

Line 2. Remove "acidity"
The change has been made.

Line 4. When it is said that is considered one of the most polluted aquatic system of the world. Some relevant numbers of the pollution should be given.
According to the reviewer comment's some relevant data about the contamination load have been included.

Line 8. The paragraph "in fact [.] REE fractionation" is unclear; rephrase the whole sentence.
The sentence has been reformulated.

Line 20. "the lower influence of mining effluents" This should be better described. "pristine", why this word is used here? Reservoirs attenuate metal concentrations. Attenuate by dilution? By precipitation?
According to the reviewer comments the sentence has been rewritten and clarified.

Lines 38---44. "Sampling was conducted in the marine domain" what does this mean? "within 30 km of coast Line" again, what does this mean? What is sampled, the Estuary, the coast or both?
No description of the difference between "Estuary" and "Mouth" and which regions they comprise are given in the text. Also, a small description of the sampling points later shown in Figure 4H (i.e. S3, S4, S6 and S7) should be done.
The whole section 3.1 should be rewritten in order to get a clear vision of how the Estuary is displayed and how the sampling has been undertaken.
According to the reviewer comments whole section 3.1 has been rewritten and clarified. Additionally the use of the term "mouth" has been clarified.

Page 6.

Line 2. Rephrase sentence in brackets.
Done.

Line 42. THAT are quantifiable.

Line 48. THAT cannot be.
Done.

Line 50. "For this reason, in THAT PREVIOUS study of our group."
Done.

Line 52 to the end of the paragraph. This EMREE parameter is crucial in this paper to prove the pollution of the Guadiana River. For this reason it is important to know how the parameter is used and how it works. Not enough details are given in this section to understand it.
As indicated in the manuscript, the EMREE parameter was proposed in a previous work (Pérez-López et al., 2010). Full details of the calculation method can be found in the online electronic supplement of that paper. However, following the reviewer's comments, we have included in this manuscript a brief description with the main details. The new lines are as follows: "The calculations are performed by defining two functions in the MREE region: (1) the polynomial curve fitting all values [$y = ax^2 + bx + c$] and (2) the straight line joining the extreme values [$y = dx + e$]. The fitting constants of both polynomial curve (a, b, c) and straight line (d, e) are obtained by the least-squares method. The value of x for the maximum vertical distance (X_{MAX}) between the polynomial curve and the line can be calculated as: $X_{MAX} = (d-b)/2a$. The y-values of the polynomial curve (Y_{MAX}) and the straight line (Y_0) defining the maximum vertical distance are obtained by substituting the X_{MAX} value in the two functions. The index E_{MREE} is defined as: $E_{MREE} = (Y_{MAX}/Y_0) - 1$ ".

Pérez-López, R., Delgado, J., Nieto, J.M., Márquez-García, B., 2010. Rare earth element geochemistry of sulphide weathering in the São Domingos mine area (Iberian Pyrite Belt): A proxy for fluid-rock interaction and ancient mining pollution. Chem. Geol. 276, 29-40.

Page 8.

Line 2 and 4. What does "environmental degradation" mean in this context?

To better explain the significance of environmental degradation the whole sentence has been rewritten.

Line 40 and 42. "The average values of these parameters for the samples of main channel, secondary tidal channels and estuary mouth are shown here in Table 1". As I said before, those three different parts of the Estuary are not explicitly described in the manuscript (Section 3.1).

According to the new section 3.1 the three parts have been described.

Line 55. Remove "may"

Done.

Line 55. Why it is said "approx. 1,30 "and "approx. 1,07"? May be they mean "average"?

The presumption is correct. The mistake has been corrected.

Page 9.

Line 8. "Slight" instead of "slightly"

Done.

Line 32. Whole paragraph. The conclusion obtained from this paragraph should be OK, but should be supported which and how numbers/data from Table 2 has been used to make the statement.

The recommendation of the reviewer has been followed.

Line 47. "and REE elements TO the fine fraction of the sediments"

Done.

Line 53---55. "confers special hydrochemical characteristics to the mixing by the existence of two processes" Rephrase.

The authors are completely in agreeing with the reviewer, and the sentence has been rewritten to improve their grammar expression.

Page 10.

Line22. "Twice" instead of "two times".

Done.

Line 32. It is true that Al and Zr do not correlate with Y/Ho ratios. I assume they muse the very low regression coefficient shown in Figure. 2D To make it clear, it will be better if R2 is given in the text.

The reviewer suggestion has been considered.

Line 38 to the end of the paragraph. Authors should be very careful here. In the previous paragraph they state that Al and Zr do not correlate with Y/Ho ratios because R2 are 0.24 and 0.38. However, in this paragraph in Figure 3F they used regression coefficients of 0.35 to conclude "moderate" correlation. Also, a correlation of 0.47 is doubtful. Finally it is said "Although based on the total concentrations of P2O5 and Zr, the percentage of phosphate minerals and zircon is negligible in the bulk sediment, but in percentage terms, these accessory minerals could play an important role controlling the REE chemistry on the Guadiana sediments". This is quite a strong statement unsupported by any number. Why in percentage terms this minerals could play an important role?"

We totally agree with this comment. Correlation coefficients between REE (La) and P₂O₅ (R² = 0.47) and REE (Yb) and Zr (R² = 0.35) are awful. Hence, accessory minerals such as phosphates and zircon do not play a significant role in the REE fractionation in the estuary sediments. In this sense, the excellent correlation between REE (La) and Th (R² = 0.81) would not help to interpret these control processes, and therefore it has been eliminated of the Figure 2E. In addition, as pointed out by the reviewer, it is “a strong statement unsupported by any number” that the total content of phosphates and zircon is negligible, but in percentage terms, these minerals could play an important role. This has been also a mistake on our part. Thus, we have clarified this whole paragraph as follows: “Some minerals identified in the sediments could also control REE fractionation. For instance, precipitation of phosphate minerals of biogenic, authigenic and diagenetic origin in acid rivers could cause well-developed MREE-enriched signatures in the sediment (e.g. Hannigan and Sholkovitz, 2001; Borrego et al., 2004). Other minerals such as zircon have significant HREE content (Yang et al., 2002). Based on the total concentrations of P₂O₅ and Zr, the percentage of phosphate minerals (mainly and apatite and monazite) and zircon is negligible in the bulk sediments (Delgado et al., 2011). Moreover, no correlations between REE (La) and P₂O₅ (R² = 0.47; Fig. 2E) and REE (Yb) and Zr (R² = 0.35; Fig. 2F) were found. Hence, these accessory minerals do not seem to control the REE chemistry on the Guadiana estuary”.

Hannigan, R.E., Sholkovitz, E.R., 2001. The development of middle rare earth element enrichments in freshwaters: weathering of phosphate minerals. Chem. Geol. 175, 495-508.

Borrego, J., López-González, N., Carro, B., Lozano-Soria, O., 2004. Origin of the anomalies in light and middle REE in sediments of an estuary affected by phosphogypsum wastes (south-western Spain). Mar. Poll. Bull. 49, 1045-1053.

Yang, S.Y., Jung, H.S., Choi, M.S., Li, C.X., 2002. The rare earth element compositions of the Changjiang (Yangtze) and Huanghe (Yellow) river sediments. Earth Planet. Sc. Lett. 201, 407-419.

Delgado, J., Barba-Brioso, C., Nieto, J.M., Boski, T., 2011. Speciation and ecological risk of toxic elements in estuarine sediments affected by multiple anthropogenic contributions (Guadiana saltmarshes, SW Iberian Peninsula): I. Surficial sediments. Sci. Total. Environ. 409, 3666–3679.

Line 57. "Hence, these data suggest that the authigenic fraction of Fe---Al oxy---hydroxides preferentially control the removal of REE from solution to the sediment" Which data? All data from Figure 2? In that case this conclusion should be in a different paragraph.

The authors are completely in agreeing with the reviewer, and the sentence has been rewritten.

Page 11.

Line 6. Section 5.2 is difficult to follow due to the lack of information of the sampling area. Mouth and Estuary are not the same according to the authors, but don't explain which is which or in which station they change their names. Also main channel and secondary channel are not described (although this is easier to infer)

According to the previous reviewer's suggestion, section 3.1 has been improved. Additionally, an explanation of the difference between main channel and mouth has been included.

Line 14. "can be visually recognized" how? Details should be done

More details have been provided in the next sentence.

Line 16. Remove accordingly.

Done.

Line 18. "Influence" instead of "affection"

Done.

Line 20---22. "The distribution REE patterns in the mouth show a general tendency to evolve from relative LREE---enriched to clearly flat patterns (Fig. 4H)". Figure 4H should be properly explained and sampling locations S---

7, S---6 etc. described (they are hidden in the map) in order to fully understand this statement.

More details about sampling point and mouth estuary sector have been provided in the next sentence. Additionally, the authors refer to the next section 3.1 previously described.

Line 22 "relative LREE enrichment" means that the HLREE enrichment is not very significant? Rephrase to make it clear. Also, again a number should be given to support the statement.

Please, note that in the beginning of the paragraph has been clarified the significance of "relative enrichment". This simply refers to an enrichment of LREE respect to HREE and MREE. The values refer to the mouth samples have been included supporting this affirmation.

Line 28. Remove basing
Done.

Line 28. The shown NASC---normalized ratios, are the average results from all the samples? Explain please.

The reviewer suggestion has been considered.

Line 30. "bears no clear conclusion for Guadiana estuary sediments" explain why is that.

The paragraph has been rewritten to better explain the interpretations about traditional ratios.

Line 30 "despite THE FACT THAT curvature of REE segments can be."

Done.

Line 34. "Hence [.] in slightly contaminated estuaries". Rephrase, too long sentence.

Line 40. Replace "slightly".

Done.

Page 12.

Line 2. "This confirms that Guadiana estuary is moderately affected by AMD discharges from the IPB". I understand that a positive EMREE parameter indicates AMD contribution. However, since not enough details are given of how this parameter works the conclusion that the estuary is MODERATELY affected is taken out of the blue. Again, this statement should be better supported, it will be enough to show the numbers from Tables and Figures that are indicating "moderate" and why this is so.

Average EMREE value has been include in the text. Additionally, the results have been compared with the pollution source area (Sao Domingos mine) to justify the moderate affection of AMD in the estuarine zone.

Line 12. Again "which suggest that MREE the estuary presents a moderate metal-- enrichment related to AMD (Delgado et al., 2010)", some of the data provided in Delgado et al. 2010 should be given here, as a support that the existence of "moderate" metallic enrichment is true. IN GENERAL. The authors want to give evidences that EMREE is a better parameter than La/Gd ratios to detect AMD pollution. The argument is that La/Gd is not able to detect AMD pollution in Guadiana River, whereas EMREE is. This is tricky, because the authors are assuming that the river is polluted. But the only real proof provided by the authors for the contamination is actually EMREE parameter, which is the one they want to verify.

In Line 12 is given a reference of heavy metal concentrations measured in the area (Delgado et. al, 2010). According to the author, these heavy metal concentrations suggest moderate metal enrichment. Again, this statement is given with no accompanying numbers to help us understand why the enrichment is "moderate". And is a shame because it is this specific reference the one that is supporting AMD pollution in the area. What I would suggest is that if possible, incorporate some of the heavy metal concentrations to the text in order to support EMREE parameter.

According to the reviewer the metal concentration and their enrichment factor respect to the Background have been include in the paragraph to support the moderate metal enrichment in the Guadiana salt marshes.

Line 34. "consistent" instead of "congruent".

Done.

Line 42 "Figure 5 depicts the good polynomial fittings of the spatial variation of REE ($R^2 = 0.88$; Fig. 5A) and EMREE ($R^2 = 0.77$; Fig. 5B) with distance". I don't see clearly the point of doing a fitting to a polynomial that doesn't have any real interpretation but a mathematical fitting. Both polynomials for REE and EMREE are of different orders, i.e. they don't even have the same shape. The two shaded areas are relatively clear for the REE graphic, but not for EMREE. Excluding the point around km 6 that reaches the highest MREE. If one focus on the blue points not clear difference can be seen from km 5 to km 25 and is not that different to La/Gd green points. The authors should use either a better description of the fitting and their arguments, either a different comparison to make their point.

We do not totally agree with the reviewer in this commentary for the following reasons:

1. *The curves resulting from the polynomial fitting simply confirm what was already observed in the Figure 1: "EMREE distribution map obtained applying spatial analysis by GIS". Therefore, these polynomials are "a mathematical fitting" of a "real interpretation". Thus, the manuscript would not lose information if we remove both polynomial fittings because the two zones of flocculation can be interpreted from the Figure 1.*

2. *Albeit, similar mathematical approaches have been previously used to interpret the distribution of REE in estuaries as a function of salinity (e.g. Hannigan et al., 2010). In turn, both salinity and distance are correlated according to the processes of mixing in an estuary. Therefore, the polynomial curves may also be used for interpretation of our results. In short, we prefer to keep this information if the Editor agrees.*

3. *We think the reviewer is slightly confused about the order of both polynomials (you could check it in the Figure 5). Both polynomials for REE and E_{MREE} are of the same order, i.e. they have the same shape!*

4. *Just using the same polynomial fitting for the La/Gd ratio, the theoretical curve is not consistent with the real results, and the correlation coefficient is poor ($R^2 < 0.4$). Given that this section of the discussion has generated confusion in the reviewer, we have performed some modifications to clarify the doubtful aspects:*

- *In the lines:*

"The influence of mixing conditions on the flocculation and removal of trace elements in the Guadiana estuary can be evidenced through the MREE enrichments in the sediments. Figure 5 depicts the spatial variation of ΣREE and E_{MREE} with distance in the main channel. The best-fitting curves of the values obtained by the method of least squares are fifth-order polynomials that would yield the same information as the spatial distribution map obtained by GIS. Both curves have the same trend and good correlation coefficients, i.e. $R^2 = 0.88$ for ΣREE (Fig. 5A) and $R^2 = 0.77$ for E_{MREE} (Fig. 5B). Similar polynomial fittings have been previously used to show the relation between REE spatial distribution and salinity in estuaries (e.g. Hannigan et al., 2010). The two zones previously observed in the map for high E_{MREE} values, i.e. Zone-A between 5 and 7 km and Zone-B between 16 and 23 km from the mouth, may be observed in the Figure 5. Zones with high REE abundance occur along the main channel where mixing of acidic fluvial water and ocean water leads to neutralization and colloidal removal of REE from the dissolved load and sequestration in the sediments".

- *In the lines:*

"Figure 5B also shows the spatial variation for the $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ratios. The best-fitting polynomial curve from this series of data points is for an order higher than the fifth and with values of $R^2 < 0.4$. This fitting would not provide any reasonable information about the processes of REE distribution in the estuary. The $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ratios would rather represent a zigzag distribution around the unity. This again suggests that the traditional parameters to identify fractionation processes in AMD-affected estuarine environments are less sensitive".

Hannigan, R., Dorval, E., Jones, C., 2010. The rare earth element chemistry of estuarine surface sediments in the Chesapeake Bay. *Chem. Geol.* 272, 20-30.

Line 46. "may be now?". Yes or no?

The mistake has been corrected.

Line 54. "is likely caused by" instead of "may be most likely."

Done.

Page 13.

Line 20. "in the channel sediment" rephrase.

Done.

Line 20. "The flocculation process recorded in the channel sediment has a spatial gap with respect to the area where AMD neutralization by mixing of river water with seawater really occurs".

Is this a conclusion from previous data? Which data? Is it an hypothesis? Flocculation location is clear, but where does the AMD neutralization take place in the area? Is it said somewhere in the text.

The paragraph has been completed to a better understanding.

AMD neutralization takes place upstream of the basin as already reported Delgado et al. (2009). Thus, based on data from previous work and in the spatial analysis of MREE, is reasonable to think that since the neutralization occurs until the final decantation process takes place, exists a spatial lag probably accentuated by the strong seasonality of river discharges and the bypassing effect in the estuarine main channel.

Line 32. "Would favour ever more", rephrase.

"even more" has been deleted.

Line 42. "Figure 5B also shows the spatial variation for the (La/Gd)NASC ratios whose zigzag distribution around unity does not fit well to a reasonable polynomial curve". Again, I don't understand this argument. The fact that EMREE can be fitted to a random polynomial doesn't prove that is working better than La/Gd ratios.

Line 46. "Given the success of the novel EMREE parameter, its extension to the scientific community is strongly recommended to study the water mixing processes in natural or AMD---affected estuaries". I would carefully use this statement.

The sentence has been rephrasing with more caution.

TABLES AND FIGURES.

Table 1. What does R2 stand for? Regression coefficient of the MREE parameter? More details of MREE and R2 should be given in the text.

Done.

Figure 2. X axis with no units or captions are a bit puzzling. Figure captions should display how to read the graphics. Also, units are missing. They are given in the fitting equations, but that should be warned somewhere.

Do you mean y axis? The authors think that the reviewer could refer to the y axis, and consequently the labels have been included. Additionally, the figure caption has been rewritten according to the suggestion.

Figure 1. Back and white figure doesn't look clear enough to describe the location of the channels.

The labels of channel have been improved.

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

Rare earth elements were analyzed in surface sediments from the Guadiana estuary ► Middle-REE enrichment was used as tracers of pollution by acid mine drainage (AMD) ► No clear conclusion could be inferred from conventional ratios such as $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ► Instead, a new parameter (E_{MREE}) was used as a more sensitive environmental tracer ► Spatial E_{MREE} distribution revealed acid mixing and flocculation processes.

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3 **Enrichment of rare earth elements as environmental tracers of**
4 **contamination by acid mine drainage in salt marshes; a new perspective**
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10 Joaquín Delgado ^{a,*}, Rafael Pérez-López ^{a,b}, Laura Galván ^c, José Miguel Nieto ^a, Tomasz Boski ^d
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16 ^aDepartment of Geology, University of Huelva, Campus 'El Carmen', 21071, Huelva, Spain

17
18 ^bInstitute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research, IDÆA - CSIC, Jordi Girona 18, 08034, Barcelona, Spain

19
20 ^cDepartment of Geodynamics and Palaeontology, University of Huelva, Campus 'El Carmen', 21071, Huelva, Spain

21
22 ^dCentre for Marine and Environmental Research, University of Algarve, 8005-139, Faro, Portugal
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* Corresponding author. Joaquín Delgado.

55 Address: Department of Geology, University of Huelva, Campus 'El Carmen', 21071, Huelva, Spain.

56 Tel.: +34-95-921-9826; fax: +34-95-921-9810

57 E-mail address: joaquin.delgado@dgeo.uhu.es
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Abstract

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4 Rare earth elements (REE) were analyzed in surface sediments from the Guadiana Estuary (SW Iberian
5 Pyrite Belt). NASC (North American Shale Composite) normalized REE patterns show clearly convex
6 curvatures in middle-REE (MREE) with respect to light- and heavy-REE, indicating acid-mixing processes
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8 between fluvial waters affected by acid mine drainage (AMD) and seawater. However, REE distributions in the
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10 mouth (closer to the coastal area) show slightly LREE-enriched and flat patterns, indicating saline-mixing
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12 processes typical of the coastal zone. NASC-normalized ratios (La/Gd and La/Yb) do not discriminate between
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14 both mixing processes in the estuary. Instead, a new parameter (E_{MREE}) has been applied to measure the
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16 curvature in the MREE segment. The values of $E_{MREE} > 0$ are indicative of acid signatures and their spatial
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18 distribution reveal the existence of two decantation zones from flocculation processes related to drought periods
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20 and flood events. Studying REE fractionation through the E_{MREE} may serve as a good proxy for AMD-pollution
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22 in estuarine environments in relation to the traditional methods.
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28 **Keywords:** Rare earth elements; Environmental proxy; Acid mine drainage; Estuary pollution; Iberian Pyrite Belt
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1. INTRODUCTION

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4 Estuarine environments are known to receive huge amounts of contaminants and are considered among the
5 most sensitive areas to the accumulation of toxic compounds. In the estuaries, sediment particles play a key role
6 in the transport of trace elements from the continent to the ocean since they can act as a source or sink to the
7 interstitial water. The estuarine processes controlling the flux and the behavior of trace elements are the salinity-
8 induced coagulation of colloids and the adsorption or desorption from the particulate material (Edmond et al.,
9 1985). Rare earth elements (REE, from La to Lu) are a coherent group of trace elements whose chemical
10 behaviors, though similar to each other, systematically change along the series. Both limited mobility and
11 fractionation capacity of the REE during weathering and sedimentation make to this element group an ideal tool
12 for evaluating the estuarine processes through the study of sediments.
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22 Concentration and fractionation patterns of REE in estuarine sediments are controlled by the fluvial
23 discharge composition and the water mixing conditions in the system (Byrne and Sholkovitz, 1996). Acid mine
24 drainage (AMD) results from oxidation of sulfides by run-off waters draining abandoned mining areas, and often
25 affects to surrounding estuarine systems (e.g. Olías et al., 2006; Nieto et al., 2007). REE fractionation has been
26 shown to be very useful for identifying salt-mixing processes in non-polluted estuaries with mixing between
27 circum-neutral river and seawater, or acid-mixing processes in estuaries receiving fluvial courses impacted by
28 AMD (e.g., Elbaz-Poulichet et al., 1999; Borrego et al., 2005). Mixing processes are often quantified according
29 to REE patterns and (La/Yb) and (La/Gd) ratios. In order to be better able to observe fractionation processes, it is
30 customary to normalize absolute REE concentrations to those in some naturally occurring material such as North
31 American Shale Composite (NASC), which is usually used in the marine geochemistry (Haskin et al., 1968).
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42 In estuarine environments not affected by acid discharges, light-REE (LREE) are preferentially adsorbed on
43 the solid particles, while middle-REE (MREE) and heavy-REE (HREE) preferentially remain in solution (e.g.
44 Elderfield et al., 1990; Sholkovitz et al., 1992; Sholkovitz, 1993; Sholkovitz, 1995; Sholkovitz and Szymczak,
45 2000; Lawrence and Kamber, 2006). When normalized against NASC, the sediments present a sub-parallel REE
46 fractionation pattern, with often a relative LREE enrichment with respect to MREE and HREE. The enrichment
47 in LREE relative to HREE is reflected by $(La/Yb)_{NASC}$ ratios above 1 and indicates estuaries only affected by
48 saline mixing processes.
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56 However, the distribution of REE in AMD discharges often shows NASC-normalized convex patterns with
57 an evident enrichment of MREE with respect to LREE and HREE (e.g. Johannesson and Lyons, 1995;
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1 Verplanck et al., 1999; Gimeno et al., 2000; Gammons et al., 2005; Olías et al., 2005; Ferreira da Silva et al.,
2 2009). The preferential sorptive removal of MREE by precipitation of poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxides,
3 typical of AMD-affected environments, favors that fluvial sediments also preserve NASC-normalized patterns
4 with convex MREE-signatures (Bau, 1999; Johannesson and Zhou, 1999). In AMD-affected estuarine
5 environments, MREE-enriched signatures in sediments are often quantified by $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ratios < 1 and
6 indicates estuaries affected by acid mixing processes, and hence, likely metal-polluted (Elbaz-Poulichet and
7 Dupuy, 1999; Borrego et al., 2004; Borrego et al., 2005). Consequently, REE patterns could be used to identify
8 water-rock interactions that govern the composition of acidic discharges from sulfide-mining wastes and as a
9 tool to assess contamination by AMD in environmental systems.

10 We report hence a comprehensive study of the REE content in surface sediments of the Guadiana river
11 estuary (SW Iberian Peninsula). This estuary is controversial because some authors have classified it as a non-
12 polluted sedimentary environment (e.g., Ruiz, 2001; González-Pérez et al., 2008), while other authors noted
13 metal concentrations in excess of background values due to AMD discharges (Delgado et al., 2010). Hence,
14 applying the REE fractionation would be a useful proxy for assessing the impact of sulfide mine-related
15 pollution. In this study, spatial variation of $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ratios in the surface sediments of this estuary was
16 analyzed to recognize REE patterns enriched in MREE, and thus, AMD-affected environments. The results were
17 compared with a new parameter, so-called E_{MREE} index, recently proposed by Pérez-López et al. (2010) as a
18 more sensitive environmental tracer especially designed for systems affected by AMD pollution.

19 The main aims of this work are: (1) to characterize concentration and spatial distribution of REE along the
20 estuary, (2) to understand the processes controlling the REE behavior in non-natural estuarine systems where
21 seawater mixes with acidic river water and, (3) to assess the possibility of using the methodology devised by
22 Pérez-López et al. (2010) as a geochemistry tool to trace contamination by AMD in estuarine systems.

23 **2. ENVIRONMENTAL SETTING**

24 The study area is located in the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB), which is the largest sulfide metallogenic province
25 in the world with an intense mining activity dating back to Third Millennium B.C. (Sáez et al., 1999; Nocete et
26 al., 2005; Delgado et al., 2012). Thenceforth, this massive sulfide belt has been a source of wealth but also of
27 pollution. Part of the courses of the Tinto, Odiel and Guadiana rivers run over the IPB and drain huge
28 contributions of AMD from oxidation of sulfide-rich mining wastes spread over more than a hundred abandoned
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1 mines around the region (Cánovas et al., 2007; Sarmiento et al., 2009; Delgado et al., 2009). Tinto and Odiel
2 rivers converge in a common estuary that receives large amounts of contaminants to the extent that is considered
3 one of the most polluted aquatic systems in the world (Nieto et al., 2007). So, recent studies suggest that both
4 rivers transport enormous quantities of dissolved contaminants: 7900 t·a⁻¹ of Fe, 5800 t·a⁻¹ Al, 3500 t·a⁻¹ Zn,
5 1700 t·a⁻¹ Cu, 1600 t·a⁻¹ Mn and minor quantities of other metals. These values represent 60% of the global gross
6 flux of dissolved Zn transported by rivers in to the ocean, and 17% of the global gross flux of dissolved Cu
7 (Olías et al., 2006). Mining pollution can even be dated from vertical sedimentary records using metal
8 concentration (López-González et al., 2006) and REE fractionation (Borrego et al., 2005).
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10 The Guadiana river basin also drains the IPB, concretely the western part of the region and its corresponding
11 estuary is open to the Atlantic Ocean at approx. 50 km from the Tinto-Odiel estuary. The main course has 810
12 km of length, of which the last 200 km constitute the natural border between Portugal and Spain. This river is the
13 main system responsible for the transport and diffusion of the pollution, from São Domingos mine in the
14 Portuguese sector and Herrerías and Thasis mines in the Spanish sector, to its estuary (Delgado et al., 2009).
15 However, compared to the Tinto-Odiel system, the lower influence of mining effluents and the existence of some
16 water reservoirs attenuating the metal concentration by dilution, favor that fluvial and estuarine sediments
17 present a less significant contamination.
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32 33 34 **3. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

35 36 37 38 **3.1. Sampling points**

39 A total of 89 samples of shallow surface sediments were collected with a manual drill in the channels of the
40 Guadiana River Estuary. Sampling was conducted in the lower estuary within 30 km of the shoreline, coinciding
41 with the marine influence according to Morales et al. (2006). Sampling points were located in the main channel
42 of the Guadiana River and the five secondary tidal channels forming the wetland area: Carrasqueira and Castro
43 Marim in Portugal, and Canela, San Bruno, Carreras in Spain (Fig. 1). Henceforth, to differentiate the samples
44 closest to the coastal line (samples S3, S4, S6 and S7) we will use the term mouth, which describe the part
45 practically open to the sea in the estuary.
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59 **3.2. Analytical procedures**

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1 Sediment samples (around 2 kg for each sample) were ground, oven-dried at 40 °C until complete dryness,
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3 homogenized and sieved (< 2 mm) for mineralogy, grain size study and geochemical analysis. Given that
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5 physical-chemical properties of water strongly influence REE geochemistry of surface sediments, some
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7 parameters such as temperature, pH and electrical conductivity using portable meters, and salinity determined
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9 from chloride concentration, were also measured at 13 points of water quality control (Fig. 1) at the time of
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11 sample collection (details above the methodology have been described by Delgado et al., 2009).
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14 Major minerals present in the samples were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD), and minor phases were
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16 detected and identified by means of scanning electron microscopy equipped with an energy dispersive system for
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18 microanalysis (SEM-EDS). The grain size study of the sediments was performed using a particle size analyzer
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20 Malvern Mastersizer 2000. Bulk composition was carried out by Acme Analytical Laboratories Ltd (Vancouver,
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22 Canada), accredited under ISO 9002, through its Italian affiliate (ERS Srl, Napoli). Sediment samples were
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24 digested by $\text{LiBO}_2\text{-Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ fusion/dilute nitric and the resulting solutions analyzed. The major and trace
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26 elements (including the REE) of solutions were analyzed by ICP-AES (inductively coupled plasma - atomic
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28 emission spectroscopy; Jarrell Ash model Atomcomp 975) and ICP-MS (inductively coupled plasma-mass
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30 spectrometry; Perkin Elmer model Elan 6000), respectively. Volatile phases were calculated by loss on ignition
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32 (LOI), and total carbon and sulfur by LECO (SC-144DR model).
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34 To demonstrate the reproducibility and accuracy of the results, the analysis sequences consisted of Acme's
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36 in-house reference materials (DS7 and SO-18), Canadian certified reference materials project (TILL-4 and
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38 LKSD-2), other certified reference materials analyzed as an unknown (STSD-1 and STSD-2, standard from
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40 stream sediments), method blanks and replicated samples. For detailed information of the results on the quality
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42 control, the reader is referred to previous works in this matter (Delgado et al., 2010).
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46 **3.3. MREE-enrichment indicator calculation**

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50 The enrichment and depletion in MREE give upward concave (V-type) and convex (Λ -type) REE patterns
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52 that are quantifiable according to the NASC-normalized $(\text{La}/\text{Gd})_{\text{NASC}}$ ratio, as stated in the Introduction.
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54 However, using a single rare earth as representative of a set could hamper the interpretation of REE patterns in
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56 the case of exclusive fractionation affecting only that rare earth. Indeed, both water-sulfide interaction and AMD
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58 production cause a curvature effect in the MREE whole segment that cannot be well-evaluated by these
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parameters (Pérez-López et al., 2010). Therefore, it would be crucial to assess the significance of the curvature effect in the MREE whole segment. For this reason, in that recent study of our group, we proposed the index E_{MREE} to quantify this effect as the normalized maximum vertical difference between the polynomial curve fitting of the MREE region and its theoretical Y-axis position in the absence of enrichment or depletion (see details of the calculation method in the on-line electronic supplement in Pérez-López et al., 2010). The calculations are performed by defining two functions in the MREE region: (1) the polynomial curve fitting all values [$y = ax^2 + bx + c$] and (2) the straight line joining the extreme values [$y = dx + e$]. The fitting constants of both polynomial curve (a, b, c) and straight line (d, e) are obtained by the least-squares method. The value of x for the maximum vertical distance (X_{MAX}) between the polynomial curve and the line can be calculated as: $X_{MAX} = (d-b)/2a$. The y-values of the polynomial curve (Y_{MAX}) and the straight line (Y_0) defining the maximum vertical distance are obtained by substituting the X_{MAX} value in the two functions. The index E_{MREE} is defined as: $E_{MREE} = (Y_{MAX}/Y_0) - 1$. The quality of the fit, and hence the significance of the curve formed by data points, was quantified by the squared correlation coefficient, R^2 . The value of E_{MREE} is positive for convex MREE-signatures, negative for concave MREE-signatures and around zero for flat patterns. The E_{MREE} parameter is more sensitive to recognize curved MREE signatures than the NASC-normalized ratios.

3.4. Geographic Information System methodology

The positions of the sampling points were recorded by GPS and the information implemented in a geographic information system (GIS) using the ArcGIS[®] software. GIS methodology was also used to represent the E_{MREE} parameter in the studied area and generate spatial distribution maps by means of the kriging interpolation technique (Webster and Oliver, 2001). For this purpose, interpolation calculations were processed into a 50 resolution raster grid (previously checked by Delgado et al. (2011) in the study area) where each pixel values express the E_{MREE} index of the REE pattern obtained in the sediment of each specific location. This tool will allow both evaluation of the E_{MREE} index as indicator of AMD pollution and search of sites of environmental vulnerability in the Guadiana river estuary.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Water environmental variables

1 Variations in pH, electrical conductivity and salinity in the water are described in Delgado et al. (2009). The
2 study area clearly shows characteristics of estuarine waters with ranges between 7.5 and 8.6 of pH, and 0.3 and
3 51 mS cm⁻¹ of electrical conductivity. Water salinity increases toward estuary mouth from 4 to 34‰. It is worth
4 to note that rivers in Mediterranean climate regions, such as the Guadiana river, alternate long drought periods
5 and short but intense rainfall events (Cánovas et al., 2010), and these parameters were measured during the
6 sediment collection in drought period.
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13 **4.2. Mineralogy and major composition of sediments**

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16 Mineralogy of the surface sediments in the Guadiana estuary is mainly composed of quartz (average of
17 70%), kaolinite-smectites (10%), illite (7%), albite (7%) and vermiculites (6%). A more exhaustive examination
18 with SEM-EDS also revealed the presence of soluble sulfate salts, poorly crystalline Fe oxy-hydroxides and
19 pyrite. Although minor, these phases are responsible for retaining metals, and hence could release the metal into
20 the water column when the environmental conditions change, causing the degradation of this ecosystem
21 (Delgado et al., 2011). Trace minerals such as apatite, monazite, zircon and titanite were also found sporadically.
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32 Average chemical composition for surface sediments, given in oxide concentration, is clearly dominated by
33 SiO₂ (60.4%) and Al₂O₃ (14.9%), in addition to appreciable amounts of Fe₂O₃ (5.71%), Na₂O (2.45%) and K₂O
34 (2.37%), as expected based on the mineralogical composition (Table S1; see electronic supplement).
35 Concentrations for the remaining elements are lower than 2%. The distribution of major oxides is very
36 homogeneous for the whole estuary. The ratio SiO₂/Al₂O₃ < 5 evidences the low textural maturity of the
37 sediments (Delgado et al., 2010). These sediments are, in general, dominated by the lime fraction, approx. 62%
38 and 72% for the samples of the main channel and secondary tidal channel, respectively. Indeed, about 97% of the
39 samples are classified as limes or sandy limes according to the diagram proposed by Folk (1954). The rest of
40 samples, i.e. RG- 1, RG- 2, S-00-14, ES-7, S-5 and S-6, are composed of sand or slightly lime sand-sized grain
41 and correspond to a sandy point-bar located in the main channel near Vila Real (Fig. 1).
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54 **4.3. REE concentration of sediments**

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1 Concentrations of all REE in the 91 samples of surface sediments of the Guadiana estuary are shown in the
2 Table S1 (see electronic supplement). Table S1 also shows the sum of total REE (Σ REE), light REE (LREE: La
3 to Eu), heavy REE (HREE: Tb to Lu), the normalized $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ and $(La/Yb)_{NASC}$ ratios, and the E_{MREE}
4 parameter for all samples. The average values of these parameters for the samples of main channel, secondary
5 tidal channels and estuary mouth are shown here in Table 1.
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9 Higher Σ REE concentrations are found in the sediments of the main channel than in estuary mouth, ranging
10 between 15 and 224 mg kg⁻¹ (average of 177 mg kg⁻¹) and between 31 and 190 mg kg⁻¹ (average of 126 mg kg⁻¹),
11 respectively. The average Σ REE values in the sediments of the secondary tidal channels are higher than that of
12 the main channel (CAR, 194 mg kg⁻¹; LEZ, 193 mg kg⁻¹; CAN, 205 mg kg⁻¹; BRU, 213 mg kg⁻¹; CARR, 191 mg
13 kg⁻¹). Note that the behavior, in separate, of LREE and HREE is similar to Σ REE, also showing concentrations
14 that be ordered as follows (Table 1): secondary tidal channels > main channel > estuary mouth.
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18 With respect to average NASC-normalized ratios for the Guadiana estuarine sediments, average
19 $(La/Yb)_{NASC}$ value is higher than unity (average of 1.30), whereas $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ is around unity (average of 1.07).
20 Both NASC-normalized ratios are similar in main channel, secondary tidal channels and mouth estuary (Table
21 1). On the other hand, the values of E_{MREE} for the REE patterns are positive ($+0.20 \pm 0.09$ with average of $R^2 =$
22 0.79). In addition to the individual values of E_{MREE} , Table S1 also includes the values of R^2 for curve fitting of
23 the MREE segments for all sediment samples (see supplementary data). Average NASC-normalized ratios
24 indicate that there is apparently no enrichment of LREE with respect to MREE, and only a slight enrichment of
25 LREE with respect to HREE is observed. Contrary, E_{MREE} parameter suggests that the REE distributions show
26 convex MREE-signatures (see discussion below).
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30 On the other hand, europium anomalies (Eu/Eu^* values calculated from the expression
31 $Eu_{NASC}/\sqrt{[Sm_{NASC} \cdot Gd_{NASC}]}$; Taylor and McLennan, 1985) range from 1.07 to 1.55, (average of 0.96) indicating a
32 lack of significant Eu anomalies typical of fluvial-estuarine systems (Goldstein and Jacobsen, 1988; Sholkovitz,
33 1992).
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36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 **5. DISCUSSION**

52 53 54 55 **5.1. REE flocculation processes**

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ΣREE concentration for the Guadiana estuary sediments (average of 182) is much higher than that for estuarine systems with sedimentation dominated by natural weathering of silicate crustal sources such as Hoogly and Krishna estuaries (average of 98 and 42, respectively; Ramesh et al., 1999) or Florida Bay (average of 10; Caccia and Millero, 2007), while similar to that for estuarine systems affected by anthropic activities such as Changjiang and Huanghe estuaries (average of 187 and 148, respectively; Yang et al., 2002) or Odiel and Tinto estuaries (average of 174 and 200, respectively; Borrego et al., 2004). This fact could suggest that REE flocculation processes in the Guadiana estuary are similar to those of the estuaries affected by AMD in the SW Iberian Peninsula (Table 2).

Flocculation processes of colloids during natural estuarine mixing of river water with seawater dominate the removal of trace metals and REE elements to the fine fraction of the sediments. The salinity gradient plays a fundamental role in controlling the flocculation of the dissolved load and consequently the composition of the sediment (Dorval et al., 2005; Hannigan et al., 2010). However, an acidic fluvial water discharge in an estuarine system confers special hydrochemical characteristics to the mixed water by the existence of two processes: the most important, the acidic neutralization and then salt-induced mixing, typical of marine estuaries (Carro et al., 2011). In AMD-affected fluvial courses, neutralization by mixing with seawater involves the flocculation of colloids formed by poorly crystalline iron oxy-hydroxides (López-González, 2009). The dissolved-colloidal REE may be scavenged onto the surface of iron oxy-hydroxides, and then coagulated and transferred into fine-sized particles (e.g. Yang et al., 2002; Censi et al., 2007). It should be emphasized that the dissolved aluminium and then transferred to the sediments by precipitation of oxy-hydroxides in estuaries from the IPB is almost as important as the iron (Olías et al., 2006).

According to the above assumptions, several linear regressions were performed to determine the relationship between the finest fraction of the sediments of the Guadiana estuary and Fe, Al and REE (Fig. 2). As expected from the literature, the fine-grained mud fraction showed a good correlation with the percentage of Fe₂O₃ ($R^2 = 0.59$) and Al₂O₃ ($R^2 = 0.71$) (Fig. 2A). Not so good correlation is achieved with heavier fractions of the sediment (data not shown). In turn, high correlation coefficients between REE and Fe ($R^2 = 0.88$; Fig. 2B) and Al ($R^2 = 0.92$; Fig. 2C) were also found.

The Y/Ho ratio is considered as a useful tool to check the contribution of terrestrial sediments to oceans. Shale or chondrite atomic Y/Ho ratios are around 55, while marine Y/Ho ratios are approx. twice higher, i.e. 90-120 (Nozaki et al., 1997). The Y/Ho ratio for the sediments from the Guadiana estuary is very close to the shale or chondrite values (on average 53.8), which indicates large contribution of terrestrial detritus (Di Leonardo et

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al., 2009). REE affinity with Al_2O_3 may also lead to believe that REE in the Guadiana estuary are also associated
with crustal sources because aluminosilicate minerals tend to have high concentrations of these elements (Graf,
1978). However, Y/Ho ratios do not correlate with Al and Zr, which are commonly thought to represent detritus
input by riverine and aeolian sources, respectively (Wehausen and Brumsack, 2000), due to the very low
regression coefficient shown in Figure 2D ($R^2=0.38$ and 0.24 respectively).

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Some minerals identified in the sediments could also control REE fractionation. For instance, precipitation
of phosphate minerals of biogenic, authigenic and diagenetic origin in acid rivers could cause well-developed
MREE-enriched signatures in the sediment (e.g. Hannigan and Sholkovitz, 2001; Borrego et al., 2004). Other
minerals such as zircon have significant HREE content (Yang et al., 2002). Based on the total concentrations of
P₂O₅ and Zr, the percentage of phosphate minerals (mainly apatite and monazite) and zircon is negligible in
the bulk sediments (Delgado et al., 2011). Moreover, no correlations between REE (La) and P₂O₅ ($R^2 = 0.47$;
Fig. 2E) and REE (Yb) and Zr ($R^2 = 0.35$; Fig. 2F) were found. Hence, these accessory minerals do not seem to
control the REE chemistry on the Guadiana estuary.

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Hence, the analyses from all data of Figure 2 suggest that the authigenic fraction of Fe-Al oxy-hydroxides
preferentially control the removal of REE from solution to the sediment.

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5.2. NASC-normalized patterns and ratios

NASC-normalized REE patterns corresponding to the surface sediments from the Guadiana estuary are
enriched in MREE compared to LREE and HREE (relative LREE enrichment), similar to the REE distribution
for Tinto and Odiel estuaries (Fig. 3). This MREE fractionation can be visually recognized in the main channel
and all secondary tidal channels, which present a noticeable enrichment in the MREE sector giving convex (Λ -
type) REE NASC-normalized patterns (Figs. 4A-G). Guadiana estuarine system is being certainly affected by
abandoned mining activities from IPB. Note that the influence of AMD on the estuarine sediments trends to
attenuate toward the estuary mouth. In this sense, Figure 3, which compares the Guadiana with other estuaries
around the World, includes the average REE-pattern obtained from the samples located in the final sector of the
estuary (described as mouth in the Section 3.1). Analyzing the individual samples in this sector (S-3 to S-7, see
Fig. 4H), the REE distribution patterns in the mouth show a general tendency to evolve from relative LREE-
enriched to clearly flat patterns. So, except the sample S6 ($La/Yb_{NASC}=0.90$), the rest of the samples present
 $La/Yb_{NASC} \geq 1$: S1 $La/Yb_{NASC}=1.11$; S2 $La/Yb_{NASC}=1.17$; S3 $La/Yb_{NASC}=1.02$; S4 $La/Yb_{NASC}=1.13$ and S7

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La/Yb_{NASC}=3.52. Indeed, the relative LREE enrichment evidences acidity consumption in the final stretch of the estuary and saline mixing processes that resemble to those described in normal estuaries such as Hoogly estuary and Florida Bay (Fig. 3).

However the discussion on the NASC-normalized ratios from all samples, i.e. (La/Yb)_{NASC} > 1 and (La/Gd)_{NASC} ≈ 1, bears no clear conclusion for Guadiana estuary sediments. Despite the fact that concave curvature of MREE segments (typical of AMD polluted systems) can be readily recognized in the patterns (Figs. 3 and 4), the values of (La/Yb)_{NASC}=1.30 and (La/Gd)_{NASC}=1.07 describe a relative enrichment of LREE, and consequently classify the whole system as a typical environment not affected by AMD, being only affected by saline mixing processes of normal estuaries. Hence, it seems to be that traditional methods based on the (La/Gd)_{NASC} and (La/Yb)_{NASC} ratios in order to differentiate the acid- and salt-mixing processes are sometimes ambiguous and could conduct to erroneous interpretation in contaminated estuaries.

5.3. E_{MREE} parameter as an indicator of AMD pollution

The E_{MREE} parameter was proposed to quantify the magnitude of the curvature in the MREE segment, and thus, to study the mixing processes in estuarine systems due to the ambiguity of the traditional methods. E_{MREE} > 0 (MREE-enriched signatures) suggests acid-mixing processes in estuarine waters, while E_{MREE} < 0 (MREE-depleted signatures) and E_{MREE} = 0 (horizontal patterns) suggest only salt-induced mixing processes. As stated before, NASC-normalized REE distributions for surface sediments of the Guadiana estuary show clearly convex (Λ-type) MREE-signatures. The positive values of E_{MREE} (+0.20 ± 0.09 with average of R² = 0.79) are consistent with the presence of a MREE enrichment observed visually in the NASC-normalized patterns, unlike conventional (La/Yb)_{NASC} and (La/Gd)_{NASC} ratios. Comparing the sediments E_{MREE} values with those of the AMD discharges (+0.72 ± 0.25) and minesoils (+0.62 ± 0.22) in São Domingos mine (Pérez-López et al., 2010), Our study confirms that Guadiana estuary is moderately affected by AMD discharges from the IPB. E_{MREE} parameter is even more sensitive to recognize pollution than other risk assessment indexes based on metal concentrations such as Müller's geoaccumulation index, which classified Guadiana estuary as a non-polluted sedimentary environment (e.g., Ruiz, 2001; González-Pérez et al., 2008). The contribution of sulfide-mining pollution is not only traced by E_{MREE} parameter but also supported by recent studies, which suggest that the estuary presents a moderate metal-enrichment related to AMD (Delgado et al., 2010). Thus, sulphide-related elements such as As (81.8 mg·Kg⁻¹), Cd (1.40 mg·Kg⁻¹), Cu (73.0 mg·Kg⁻¹), Pb (62.5 mg·Kg⁻¹) and Zn (483

1 mg·Kg⁻¹) show enrichment factors of 1.77, 1.94, 1.86, 1.84 and 2.47, exceeding the background values
2 established by Delgado et al. (2012). In fact, contaminants are found in the mobile fraction of the sediments
3 composed mainly of fine-sized reactive phases such as soluble sulfate salts, poorly crystalline Fe oxy-hydroxides
4 and sulfides (Delgado et al. 2011).
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7 The E_{MREE} parameter of the shallow sediments along the Guadiana estuary varied significantly according to
8 the distribution maps obtained by ARCGIS software (Fig. 1). E_{MREE} spatial distribution clearly shows a zone of
9 high values (red range, $E_{MREE} > 0.5$) located between Vila Real and Ayamonte villages (Zone-A, Fig. 1), which
10 was recently classified as the zone of highest vulnerability in the Guadiana saltmarshes due to their geochemical
11 anomalies with respect to the background metal content (Delgado et al., 2011). In addition, a large section of the
12 Guadiana main channel with high E_{MREE} values of around 0.2-0.3 (sky-blue range) upstream of the international
13 bridge can be also recognized (Zone-B, Fig. 1). The E_{MREE} parameter decreases progressively downstream from
14 Ayamonte village to the estuary mouth where values are close to zero. This decrease in the MREE enrichment is
15 consistent with the evolution showed by the NASC-normalized patterns in the Figure 4H, which reflects that
16 marine conditions are attained in the samples collected in coastal areas (Sholkovitz et al., 1999).
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19 The influence of mixing conditions on the flocculation and removal of trace elements in the Guadiana estuary
20 can be evidenced through the MREE enrichments in the sediments. Figure 5 depicts the spatial variation of
21 ΣREE and E_{MREE} with distance in the main channel. The best-fitting curves of the values obtained by the method
22 of least squares are fifth-order polynomials that would yield the same information as the spatial distribution map
23 obtained by GIS. Both curves have the same trend and good correlation coefficients, i.e. $R^2 = 0.88$ for ΣREE
24 (Fig. 5A) and $R^2 = 0.77$ for E_{MREE} (Fig. 5B). Similar polynomial fittings have been previously used to show the
25 relation between REE spatial distribution and salinity in estuaries (e.g. Hannigan et al., 2010). The two zones
26 previously observed in the map for high EMREE values, i.e. Zone-A between 5 and 7 km and Zone-B between
27 16 and 23 km from the mouth, may be observed in the Figure 5. Zones with high REE abundance occur along
28 the main channel where mixing of acidic fluvial water and ocean water leads to neutralization and colloidal
29 removal of REE from the dissolved load and sequestration in the sediments. The existence of two flocculation
30 points displaced in the distance is likely caused by the seasonality of Mediterranean rivers. Zone-B would
31 represent the coagulation area where the preferential removal of dissolved REE takes place in drought periods.
32 Instead, Zone-A likely reflects the displacement of the flocculation processes during flood events. During
33 rainfall events, most of the riverwater discharge, dissolved contaminant, and suspended matter transport occurs
34 in rivers from the IPB, which displace downward the coagulation processes (Delgado et al., 2009; Cánovas et al.,
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2010). The river inputs to the Guadiana estuary are highly variable, which ranged at a seasonal and inter-annual scale from <10 to $4660 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the period 1947-2001 (Garel et al., 2009). The propagation of saline intrusion in the estuary varies depending on the magnitude of river flow, and there may be a difference of up to 20 km between periods of low and high flow rates (Oliveira et al., 2006). Indeed, this difference approximates the distance existing between both points of flocculation (Fig. 5). Flocculation processes of REE in both zones are linked to the MREE fractionation associated with the formation of fine-grained colloids of iron oxy-hydroxides, which would explain the concomitant variation of ΣREE and E_{MREE} .

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The flocculation process recorded in the estuarine main channel has a spatial gap with respect to the area where AMD neutralization by mixing of river water with seawater really occurs, which could be produced upstream according to Delgado et al. (2009). In fact, both flocculation zones observed in Figure 5 are in an area of the estuary where water is characterized by pH values typical of marine conditions. For this reason, this spatial gap probably is caused by the time that elapses from the onset of nucleation of colloids until the sediment particles have a size large enough to decant and be part of the shallow sediment. In addition, in the Guadiana river estuary the volume of water that circulates in the main channel tends to maintain a sedimentary bypassing towards the coast (Morales et al., 2006), which would favour the existence of large distances between the flocculation and decantation points. Similarly, this process also explains because the salt-induced flocculation typical of marine estuaries observed in the sediments from the mouth, which dominates in low salinity regions (Sholkovitz, 1995; Biati and Karbassi, 2010), does not match with the water salinity gradient (Fig. 5A).

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Figure 5B also shows the spatial variation for the $(\text{La}/\text{Gd})_{\text{NASC}}$ ratios. The best-fitting polynomial curve from this series of data points is for an order higher than the fifth and with values of $R^2 < 0.4$. This fitting would not provide any reasonable information about the processes of REE distribution in the estuary. The $(\text{La}/\text{Gd})_{\text{NASC}}$ ratios would rather represent a zigzag distribution around the unity. This again suggests that the traditional parameters to identify fractionation processes in AMD-affected estuarine environments are less sensitive. Given the success of the novel E_{MREE} parameter, the authors recommended its application for studying the water mixing processes in natural or AMD-affected estuaries.

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6. CONCLUSIONS

Guadiana river receives acid mine drainage (AMD) from oxidation of sulfide-rich wastes of abandoned mining districts from the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB; SW Iberian Peninsula). Metal pollution is considerably diluted

1 and attenuated in the river, which flows into an estuary historically considered non-polluted. However, in the
2 current study we demonstrate that Guadiana estuary are being certainly affected by current mining activities
3 from the IPB through studying the concentration variations of rare earth elements (REE) in the surface
4 sediments. Flocculation reactions by neutralization occurring within the estuary, i.e. precipitation of iron and
5 aluminum oxy-hydroxides, preferentially remove MREE from solution. Consequently, NASC-normalized
6 patterns corresponding to the sediments from the main and secondary tidal channels show convex MREE-
7 signatures. A new convexity metric (E_{MREE} parameter) reported in previous studies was used to assess the
8 significance of the curvature effect in the MREE whole segment, and hence, quantify the effects of AMD
9 pollution. This index was a more sensitive tool to recognize convex MREE signatures than other NASC-
10 normalized ratios where a single element represents to a set such as $(\text{La/Gd})_{\text{NASC}}$. Spatial E_{MREE} distribution
11 revealed two zones where decantation of fine-sized particles from flocculation by acid mixing processes occurs
12 in the estuary. The first upstream zone is larger and represents flocculation during long drought periods, while
13 the second downstream zone is smaller and represents flocculation during short but intense rainfall events.
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Table 1.- Statistical parameters of the REE (Σ REE as total REE, LREE as sum of light REE and HREE as sum of heavy REE), as well as $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ and $(La/Yb)_{NASC}$ ratios, for sediment samples from the subsystems of the Guadiana estuary. Enrichments of MREE (E_{MREE} parameter and curve fitting coefficient, R^2) are also shown.

	Σ REE	LREE	HREE	$(La/Gd)_{NASC}$	$(La/Yb)_{NASC}$	E_{MREE}	R^2
Main Channel							
Min	14.9	13.16	1.69	0.94	1.04	0.13	0.14
Max	224	199	25.1	1.20	1.46	0.50	0.96
Mean	177	158	19.2	1.07	1.27	0.21	0.79
SD	10.3	9.16	1.12	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.17
Estuary Mouth							
Min	31.1	27.2	3.81	0.87	0.90	0.04	0.37
Max	190	170	20.6	1.94	3.52	0.16	0.79
Mean	127	113	13.5	1.09	1.30	0.12	0.58
SD	15.0	13.5	1.69	0.07	0.19	0.06	0.20
CAR Tidal Channel							
Min	171	153	18.1	1.02	1.06	0.11	0.58
Max	211	189	22.2	1.15	1.31	0.29	0.96
Mean	195	174	21.0	1.07	1.20	0.21	0.82
SD	3.66	3.28	0.39	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.11
LEZ Tidal Channel							
Min	165	147	18.3	1.03	1.11	0.13	0.49
Max	208	186	23.3	1.16	1.35	0.27	0.91
Mean	193	172	20.7	1.10	1.24	0.19	0.76
SD	3.43	3.18	0.30	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.14
CAN Tidal Channel							
Min	192	172	20.7	1.02	1.11	0.24	0.80
Max	220	198	23.0	1.11	1.31	0.30	0.97
Mean	205	183	21.7	1.07	1.23	0.27	0.91
SD	3.07	2.85	0.25	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.06
BRU Tidal Channel							
Min	195	173	21.7	1.08	1.14	0.10	0.48
Max	223	198	24.2	1.17	1.36	0.19	0.85
Mean	213	190	22.8	1.11	1.26	0.15	0.72
SD	4.14	3.81	0.45	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.15
CARR Tidal Channel							
Min	148	133	14.8	0.98	1.14	0.13	0.68
Max	210	188	22.2	1.27	1.58	0.26	0.97
Mean	191	171	20.0	1.10	1.30	0.20	0.81
SD	4.02	3.57	0.48	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.10

REE values in $mg\ Kg^{-1}$, Min, Minimum. Max, Maximum. SD, Standard deviation

Table 2.- Comparative between REE content (mg kg⁻¹) and most important parameters for the Guadiana estuary and other estuarine systems around the world affected or not- by anthropogenic contributions.

	NASC	Changjiang	Huanghe	Odiel	Tinto	Florida Bay	Hoogly	Krishna	Guadiana
		(a)	(a)	(b)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(d)	This study
La	32	-	-	25.3	43.0	2.0	21.6	8.4	36.8
Ce	73	-	-	85.1	80.9	3.8	41.9	17.0	75.6
Pr	7.9	-	-	7.8	9.3	0.5	5.0	2.0	8.82
Nd	33	-	-	30.7	36.4	2.0	15.9	6.8	33.5
Sm	5.7	-	-	6.9	7.9	0.4	3.2	1.6	6.67
Eu	1.2	-	-	1.5	1.8	0.1	0.6	0.4	1.42
Gd	5.2	-	-	6.7	7.5	0.4	3.5	1.8	5.52
Tb	0.9	-	-	0.9	1.0	0.1	0.4	0.3	0.93
Dy	5.8	-	-	4.8	5.3	0.4	2.9	1.6	5.22
Ho	1	-	-	0.9	1.1	0.1	0.7	0.4	1.04
Er	3.4	-	-	1.1	2.9	0.3	1.5	0.9	3.03
Yb	3.1	-	-	2.0	2.4	0.2	1.4	0.9	2.85
Lu	0.5	-	-	0.3	0.4	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.43
ΣREE	173	187	148	174	200	10.36	98.63	42.2	182
LREE	153	168	133	157	179	8.87	88.07	36.2	163
HREE	1.15	18.3	15.2	19.9	16.7	20.5	1.49	10.6	17.9
L/HREE	133	9.19	8.72	7.90	10.7	0.43	58.98	3.43	9.08
La/Gd <small>(NASC)</small>	1	1.07	1.02	0.61	0.93	0.78	1.00	0.74	1.09
La/Yb <small>(NASC)</small>	1	1.54	1.39	1.24	1.76	0.89	1.54	0.90	1.26

a) Yang et al. (2002); b) Borrego et al. (2004); c) Caccia et al. (2007); d) Ramesh et al. (1999)

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1.- Regional setting of the study area showing the sampling points, water quality control sites and the E_{MREE} distribution map obtained applying spatial analysis by GIS throughout the different subsystems of the Guadiana estuary.

Fig. 2.- Several linear regressions showing the different sources of REE in the Guadiana salt marshes sediments: **A)** Fe_2O_3 (%) and Al_2O_3 (%) versus mud content, **B and C)** REE versus Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 content, respectively, **D)** Zr and Al_2O_3 content versus Y/Ho ratio, **E)** P_2O_5 and Th versus REE (La) content and **F)** REE (Yb) versus Zr content. R^2 represent the curve fitting of the different parameter under study. Major elements are expressed in % and trace elements in $mg \cdot Kg^{-1}$.

Fig. 3.- Comparative diagram showing NASC-normalized REE patterns for sediments of the Guadiana estuary, mouth of the Guadiana river, estuarine systems affected by AMD (Tinto and Odiel, Borrego et al., 2004) and other estuaries around the world only affected by salt mixing processes (Hoogly, Ramesh et al., 1999; Florida Bay, Caccia and Millero, 2007).

Fig. 4.- NASC-normalized REE patterns for sediment samples from the subsystems of the Guadiana Estuary: **A)** main channel and **B-F)** secondary tidal channels. **G)** Average REE pattern for all samples from the Guadiana estuary. The shadowed area refers to the variability range and dash line to the mean value. **H)** Comparative between the average REE pattern for the Guadiana estuary (dashed blue line) and the spatial evolution of the patterns in the final sector of the mouth, as well as their average value (dashed red line).

Fig. 5.- Behaviour of **(A)** total REE content and salinity, and **(B)** E_{MREE} parameter vs. $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ratio in the Guadiana main channel based on the spatial location of the samples. Note the hypothetical flocculation zones according to the seasonal river inputs.

Figure 1_BW version

Figure 1 colour

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Supplementary Data

[Click here to download Supplementary Data: Electronic supplement - Table S1.xls](#)